

**DEVELOPING STUDENT SPEECH BY TEACHING VOCABULARY
TO STUDENTS IN PRIMARY GRADES**

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The fact that Uzbekistan has turned to the world, has entered the process of progress and renewal, and that science and culture have been freed from the shackles of ideology that does not serve the interests of the nation, puts very important and urgent tasks before our scientists. Thanks to the independence, not only the heritage of our ancestors, but also the heritage of our brotherly peoples, the opportunity to boldly approach the important modern problems of science, to study the achievements of science and culture of different nations in depth along with the creativity of our contemporaries, and to apply them to our lives, that is, to further develop all aspects of our society.

The roots of the scientific potential of our country are extremely deep and strong. Therefore, the science of linguistics, which has deep roots, is responsible for analyzing and researching the issues that need to be solved in connection with the new historical reality that has arisen in our country only at the level of the interests of the free people and the requirements of the idea of national independence. This requires that the selected problems correspond to world standards according to the importance, relevance, and innovation of research methods, and at the same time, they can fully demonstrate their national identity.

In the current educational system, a new concept of acquiring knowledge - non-traditional education requires the use of various methods of technology. If we look at the educational process as a system, its constituent elements include: educational goal, expected results, teacher, student, educational content, educational method, form and tools, control and assessment. When designing the

educational process, if one of these elements is left out or not selected correctly, the system will not work, which means that the educational goal cannot be achieved.

It is known to everyone that the mother tongue and the spirit of the nation are necessary in order to bring up any perfect and mature person to adulthood. Young people should be given such an educational foundation in primary grades. In the current period, in the process of rapid civilization, "Fnewspaper due to the growing interest in science and technology; Every day new terms are introduced from magazines and fiction.¹ Many of these terms and transterms are found in the texts given in primary school textbooks. I took this topic as the subject of a monograph, taking into account the fact that elementary school students need to deeply understand the meanings of certain words in the language in order to develop their thinking and oral speech.

The analysis of scientific and technical terms, their scientific aspect, scientific problems were researched by academician Makhojiyev, Q.Zokirov, VNMusayeva and others from Uzbek terminologists. Russian and foreign scientists include Volkova, Gerd, Golovin, Grinyev, Danilenko, and others in *Bek language by F. Ibragimova*², *NM Makhmudov*³, *A. Madvaliyev*⁴ and *G. Ismailov*⁵ who conducted scientific research on this topic.

If we set the goal of applying and analyzing the terms and transterms given in primary school reading lessons, the following will be done for the first time based on the creation of methods of researching them in classes:

¹А.А.Реформатский. Введение в языкознание, М., 1955, стр. 80,

²Ибрагимова Ф. Э. Бадий матнда эллипсис ва антиэллипсис: Филол. фан. ном. ... диссертация автореф.– Ташкент, 2011. .

³Махмудов Н.М. Эллипсис в узбекском языке: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. –Т., 1977.

⁴А. Madvaliyev O'zbek terminologiyasi va leksikografiyasi masalalari "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. Toshkent, 2017

⁵ G'.Ismoilov. O'zbek tili terminologik tizimlarida semantik usulda termin hosil bo'lishi. Nomz.dis...avtoref. – Toshkent, 2011. 8-bet.

- 1) to reveal the nature of the terms and transterms given in the primary school curriculum and to determine the range of issues and problems related to them;
- 2) to identify and highlight the appropriate options of modern pedagogical technologies that are useful in teaching the terms and transterms given in primary school reading;
- 3) putting into practice the methods used in teaching the terms and transterms given in the elementary school.

Bto determine the nature of the terms given in the reading materials of the high school class and theirto study the modern pedagogical methods of teaching, to select the necessary recommendations and implement them in practice.

References

1. А.А.Реформатский. Введение в языкознание, М., 1955, стр. 80,
2. Ибрагимова Ф. Э. Бадиий матнда эллипсис ва антиэллипсис: Филол. фан. ном. ... диссертация автореф.– Тошкент, 2011.
3. Махмудов Н.М. Эллипсис в узбекском языке: Автореф. дис. ...канд. филол. наук. –Т., 1977.
4. А. Madvaliyev O‘zbek terminologiyasi va leksikografiyasi masalalari “O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi” Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. Toshkent, 2017.
5. G‘.Ismoilov. O‘zbek tili terminologik tizimlarida semantik usulda termin hosil bo‘lishi. Nomz.dis...avtoref. – Toshkent, 2011. 8-bet.